

Ni^{II} complexes of large ring tetraazamacrocycles derived from 3,4-hexanedione and diaminoalkanes

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Abstract : Ni^{II} complexes of composition [NiL(NO₃)₂] (where L = tetraazamacrocycle having 14- to 28-membered ring) have been synthesized by template condensation of 3,4-hexanedione with diaminoalkanes. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, magnetic moments and IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, nickel(II), diaminoalkanes, 3,4-hexanedione.

Ni^{II} complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from the condensation of 2,3-hexanedione with diaminoalkanes have been reported earlier from our laboratories¹. The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of Ni^{II} complexes of 14- to 28-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from 3,4-hexanedione and diaminoalkanes such as 1,3-diaminopropane, 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane and 1,10-diaminodecane.

Results and discussion

Ni^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles were synthesized by the 2+2 cyclocondensation reactions of α -diketones and diaminoalkanes in the presence of nickel(II) nitrate (Scheme 1).

The elemental analyses of the complexes confirm their stoichiometry (Table 1). The complexes are coloured solids and generally decompose on heating. They are insoluble in water, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, nitromethane and methanol but are readily soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide.

Molar conductances of 10⁻³ molar solutions of the complexes in DMSO are found in the range 56–91 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ (Table 1) indicating them to be 2 : 1 electrolytes. Thus it appears that the nitrate groups which are coordinated in solid state are displaced in solution by the solvent molecules.

The magnetic moments of Ni^{II} complexes at room temperature lie in the range 2.89–3.26 B.M. (Table 1)

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Ni^{II} macrocyclic complexes.

which are consistent with high-spin d^8 configuration of Ni^{II} and indicate distorted octahedral environment around the metal ion. The μ_{eff} values slightly higher than the spin only value (2.87 B.M.) may be due to orbital contribution². For Ni^{II} complexes of a macrocycle derived from 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione and 2,6-diaminopyridine, μ_{eff} values have been reported³ in the range 3.15–3.30 B.M.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes exhibit bands in 16500–19245 and 27000–28000 cm⁻¹ regions which can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. These are consistent with

Table 1. Analysis and physical characteristics of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}

Complex	Yield (%)	Colour and temp. of decomp. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in DMSO	μ_{eff} B.M.
			N	Ni		
[Ni(Et ₄ [14]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	41	Purple 295	11.71 (11.50)	12.20 (12.04)	83	3.24
[Ni(Et ₄ [16]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	48	Green 196	11.01 (10.87)	11.55 (11.39)	75	2.89
[Ni(Et ₄ [18]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	39	Green 178	10.53 (10.31)	10.68 (10.80)	91	3.24
[Ni(Et ₄ [22]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	64	Green 305	9.44 (9.34)	9.78 (9.79)	78	3.17
[Ni(Et ₄ [24]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	46	Green 315	8.74 (8.93)	9.58 (9.35)	72	3.23
[Ni(Et ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	34	Green 330	8.35 (8.54)	8.94 (8.95)	59	3.26
[Ni(Et ₄ [28]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	43	Green 325	8.07 (8.19)	8.73 (8.58)	56	3.02

the distorted octahedral geometry around the metal ion. In Ni^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from benzil and *m*-phenylenediamine the bands at 17500 and 27500 cm⁻¹ have been attributed to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively⁴. Similarly the bands at 18000–19000 and 29500 cm⁻¹ to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively for Ni^{II} complexes of the macrocycle 2,13-dimethyl-3,6,9,12,18-pentaazabicyclo[12.3.1]octadeca-1(18),14,16-triene⁵.

The IR spectra of Ni^{II} complexes show a medium to strong intensity band in 1550–1620 cm⁻¹ region which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ⁶ mode. The non observed of bands due to free amino or keto groups at 3400 and 1700 cm⁻¹ respectively suggested the condensation of C=O groups of the α -diketones with the -NH₂ groups of the diamines⁷. The bands observed in 1000–1040 and 1460–1500 cm⁻¹ regions confirm the monodentate coordination mode of the nitrate group⁸.

FAB mass spectra : FAB mass spectra of three complexes [Ni(Et₄[24]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂], [Ni(Et₄[26]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂] and [Ni(Et₄[28]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂] have been recorded using NBA matrix. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the three complexes exhibit less abundant peaks due to the molecular ions (M⁺) at *m/z* 626 (1.4%), 654 (2.1%) and 682 (0.9%) respectively and due to the macrocycles (L⁺) at *m/z* 444 (1.2%), 472 (2.1%) and 500 (2.0%) respectively. In the mass spectra of lanthanide(III) complexes of the macrocycle derived from 2,6-bis(2-formylphenoxy)-

methylpyridine) and 1,2-diaminoethane a peak occurs at *m/z* 372 due to the macrocycle⁹. The alkaline earth metal complexes of the macrocycles derived from furan-2,5-dicarbaldehyde and 3,6,9-trioxaundecane-1,11-diamine or 1,5-bis(2-aminophenoxy)-3-oxapentane, have been reported to exhibit peaks corresponding to the macrocycles¹⁰. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, all the three Ni^{II} complexes exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycles and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern of the complex [Ni(Et₄[26]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂] is given in Scheme 2.

There are three possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex :

(A) In this pathway two ethyl groups are simultaneously lost from the molecular ion to give a peak at *m/z* 596 (5.2%). Simultaneous loss of another ethyl group and one nitrate group gives a peak at *m/z* 505 (4.5%). Loss of remaining ethyl group, nitrate group and metal ion from the macrocyclic framework gives a peak at *m/z* 356 (1.4%) due to the species 2.

(B) In this pathway two nitrate groups and the metal ion are removed from the macrocyclic complex giving a peak at *m/z* 472 (2.4%) due to the macrocycle (L⁺). Loss of four ethyl groups gives a peak at *m/z* 351 (1.4%) due to the species 2.

(C) In this pathway, two nitrate and three methyl groups are lost from the molecular ion to give a peak at *m/z* 485 (6.2%). Finally the loss of remaining ethyl group, three

CH_2 groups and metal ion gives a peak at m/z 356 (1.4%) due to the species 2.

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{Et}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Experimental

Materials and methods: $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) was of A.R. grade. 3,4-Hexanedione (Aldrich), 1,3-diaminopropane (Merck), 1,4-diaminobutane (Merck) were purified by distillation before use. 1,7-Diaminoheptane (Merck), 1,8-diaminooctane (Merck), 1,9-diaminononane (Merck) and 1,10-diaminodecane (Fluka) were used as supplied.

Nickel was determined volumetrically by back titration with EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Conductances of the complexes were measured with the help of a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304 using 10^{-3} M solution in DMSO. The Gouy method was used for the determination of magnetic susceptibilities. IR spectra of KBr pellets of the samples were recorded in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Jasco-7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mV) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of Ni^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles: $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.74 mmol, 0.507 g) was dissolved in ~ 20 ml of *n*-butanol and to this a solution of 3,4-hexanedione (3.48 mmol, 0.398 g in ~ 20 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. This was followed by the dropwise addition of 1,3-diaminopropane (3.48 mmol, 0.258 g) in *n*-butanol (~ 20 ml) with stirring which was continued for ~ 5 h. A purple solid appeared which was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under vacuum.

A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of Ni^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from 3,4-hexanedione and other diamines such as 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane and 1,10-diaminodecane.

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